

**JOURNAL OF ADVANCED
SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH**

ISSN: 0976-9595

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RESULTS OF EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON HILL SEEDING OF MUNG BEANS

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Abstract: The article presents the results of experimental research aimed at determining the optimal number of hole groups on the sowing disk and the deviation angle of these holes relative to the disk radius for hill seeding of mung bean seeds.

Keywords: pneumatic seeding machine, seeds, machine speed, seeding accuracy, disc rotation speed, coefficient of variation, nest formation, experimental research

Among legume crops, mung beans rank second in the world after soybeans in terms of cultivated area [1]. The precise seeding rate and method are among the most important factors determining yield. Scientific sources provide information on the advantages of hill seeding of mung beans compared to row (drill) seeding [2].

To ensure hill seeding, suction holes on the sowing disk must be arranged in groups and have a certain number.

In order to determine the optimal number of suction holes per group on the sowing disk, three different disks were prepared, with 38, 42, and 46 holes per group, each hole having a diameter of 3 mm. The diameter of the middle concentric row of holes on these disks corresponded to the diameter of the row seeding disk, i.e., 195 mm, while the outer row had a diameter of 209 mm.

The rotational speed of the sowing disk was set based on a disk diameter of 195 mm. In this case, the rotational speed was determined according to the average diameter between the two rows of holes, which amounted to 202 mm.

The experiments were carried out according to the hill seeding pattern of 10×2 (distance between hills – 10 cm, number of seeds per hill – 2), with the seeder's forward speed ranging from 1.39 m/s to 2.23 m/s, with an interval of 0.28 m/s (Figure 1).

From the data presented in Figure 1, it can be observed that when mung beans were sown according to the 10×2 seeding scheme, the sowing disk with 38 hole groups showed the lowest performance. As the seeder's forward speed increased from 1.39 m/s to 2.23 m/s, the seeding accuracy decreased from 90.9% to 70.2%. When the sowing disk had 42 hole groups, the seeding accuracy was the highest. With an increase in the seeder's forward speed from 1.39 m/s to 2.23 m/s, the seeding accuracy ranged from 94.0% to 85.5%, and the accuracy curve had a parabolic shape. For the sowing disk with 46 hole groups, the seeding accuracy was lower compared to the disk with 42 hole groups. As the seeder's forward speed increased from 1.39 m/s to 2.23 m/s, the seeding accuracy changed from 92.5% to 80.1%. The required seeding accuracy for the disks with 38, 42, and 46 hole groups

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corresponded to seeder forward speeds of 1.67 m/s, 2.23 m/s, and 1.95 m/s, respectively.

1,2,3 – Number of hole groups on the sowing disk: 38, 42, and 46, respectively

Figure 1. Dependence of seeding accuracy (Te) on seeder forward speed (Vc)

It should be noted that, in order to ensure uniform conditions for withdrawing seeds from the general mass in the seed receiving chamber, the rotational speeds of different disks vary even when the seeding unit operates at the same drive speed (Table).

Table

Seeding quality of the pneumatic device equipped with sowing disks having different hole groups

(seeding scheme: 10 cm spacing)

Number of hole groups	Seeding speed, Vc, m/s	Rotational speed of metering rotor, U ₀ , min ⁻¹	Seeding accuracy, Tv, %	Single-seed hills, %	Quadratic deviation, ±σ, %	Variation coefficient, V, %
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
38	1,39	22	90,9	5,0	0,27	13,7
	1,67	26	87,6	6,6	0,32	15,7
	1,95	31	80,2	11,6	0,39	19,5
	2,23	35	70,2	18,2	0,53	28,0
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

42	1,39	20	94,0	4,3	0,21	10,4
	1,67	24	92,3	5,1	0,24	12,4
	1,95	28	90,6	6,0	0,37	18,8
	2,23	32	85,5	8,5	0,45	23,2
46	1,39	18	92,5	5,0	0,29	14,8
	1,67	22	90,7	6,2	0,34	16,9
	1,95	25	88,2	7,5	0,40	20,1
	2,23	29	80,1	12,4	0,49	25,0

From the table, it can be seen that with an increase in the seeder's forward speed, the seeding accuracy decreased due to a reduction in the number of seeds per hill compared to the set value. When the sowing disk had 38 hole groups and the seeder's forward speed increased from 1.39 m/s to 2.23 m/s, the number of single-seed hills rose from 5.0% to 18.2%. For disks with 42 and 46 hole groups, this indicator increased from 4.3% to 8.5% and from 5.0% to 12.4%, respectively.

The experiments were conducted with a seeder forward speed of 1.67 m/s and a hill spacing of 10 cm, and continued at intervals within the range of 1.39 to 2.23 m/s (Figure 2).

1,2,3,4 – Deviation angle relative to the radial direction: 0, 10, 20, and 30°

Figure 2. Dependence of hill length (l_d) on seeder forward speed (V_c) and the deviation angle (γ) of suction holes relative to the disk radius

From the data presented in Figure 2, it can be seen that in all variants, an increase in the elongation index of hill length was observed, with the smallest elongation occurring when the deviation angle of suction holes relative to the disk radius was 20°. In this case, the deviation angle ensured the sequential removal of seeds from the suction zone through the holes and their placement in the furrow opened by the coulter with a minimum hill length.

When suction holes were arranged along the disk radius, the hill length at a seeder forward speed of 1.39 m/s was 2.8 cm. With deviation angles of 10°, 20°, and 30°, the hill length was 2.6 cm, 2.3 cm, and 2.4 cm, respectively. In the experimental studies, the maximum hill length (from 2.8 cm to 3.8 cm) was recorded when suction holes were positioned along the disk radius.

When the seeder's forward speed increased from 1.39 m/s to 2.23 m/s, at a deviation angle of 20° relative to the disk radius, the hill elongation increased from 2.3 cm to 2.9 cm. For deviation angles of 0°, 10°, and 30°, this indicator varied within 2.8–3.8 cm, 2.6–3.5 cm, and 2.4–3.2 cm, respectively.

Thus, it can be concluded that hill elongation is influenced both by the deviation angle of suction holes relative to the disk radius and by the seeder's forward speed.

Conclusion

In hill seeding of mung beans, the sowing disk with 42 suction holes demonstrated the highest seeding accuracy. As the seeder's forward speed increased from 1.39 m/s to 2.23 m/s, the accuracy ranged from 94.0% to 85.5%. The minimum hill elongation was achieved when the deviation angle of suction holes relative to the disk radius, measured from the centers of holes within a group, was 25°. In this case, depending on the forward speed, the hill length during hill seeding of mung beans was 2.3–2.8 cm.

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